

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH IN GENDER DIFFERENCES

Hajiyeva M.

Associate Professor, Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction

Abstract

This article examines gender differences in vocabulary from a cognitive linguistics perspective. It examines the influence of cognitive processes on the perception and use of language by men and women. It focuses on how different cognitive structures associated with gender identity influence word choice, meaning formation, and interpretation. The article analyzes examples of lexical differences in the speech of men and women, including both referential and metaphorical differences. Conceptual metaphors related to gender and their influence on the lexical content of language are also considered.

Linguistic studies of gender differences in speech practices are an important area of study in sociolinguistics. Research shows that language not only reflects but also constructs gender roles in society. This article examines key aspects of differences in the speech of men and women, their sociocultural determinacy, and their interaction with social structures. The focus is on theoretical approaches to analyzing gender differences, as well as empirical research, including those focusing on differences in vocabulary, intonation, forms of address, and emotional expression in the speech practices of men and women. Stereotypes related to language use and their influence on the perception of social roles in modern society are also discussed.

Keywords: gender differences, sociolinguistics, gender and language, stereotypes, gender identity, speech practices, vocabulary, intonation, sociocultural norms.

Cognitive linguistics, as an interdisciplinary field, considers language as a phenomenon closely related to the processes of thinking, perception, and social structures. One of the most interesting topics in cognitive linguistics is the study of how gender differences affect lexical perception and language use. Gender, as a social and cultural category, permeates all levels of language, from phonetics and grammar to vocabulary and phraseology. Language, in turn, not only reflects gender differences, but also actively shapes ideas about the roles of men and women in society.

Linguistic studies of gender differences occupy an important place in sociolinguistics, as language is one of the main tools through which gender roles and social stereotypes are expressed and consolidated. Language reflects not only the biological differences between men and women, but also the cultural, historical, and social conditions of their interaction. Gender differences in speech practices manifest themselves in various aspects, from vocabulary and grammatical constructions to intonation and communication style. These differences can influence the perception of individuals in society and the formation of stereotypical images of male and female roles [6].

In the field of linguistics, there are several theories explaining gender differences in language. Deborah Tannen, a famous American linguist, in her book "You just don't understand: Women and men in conversation" argues that men and women use different communication strategies, which is related to their social roles: men tend to be more aggressive and competitive in their communication style, while women tend to be cooperative and empathic [5].

It is also important to note the work of Peter Trager and Robert Lang, who argue that gender differences in language can be seen as the result of broader social and cultural practices, where language serves as one of the tools for maintaining hierarchies in society.

The vocabulary of a language is an important part of its structure, which is closely related to the perception of the surrounding world and to social, cultural and cognitive processes. One of the most interesting aspects in the study of vocabulary is its gender component. Gender, as a social and cultural category, influences the use of words and expressions, reflecting and reinforcing stereotypes about men and women. Language not only reflects social and cultural norms, but also actively forms ideas about the roles that are attributed to different genders in society.

One of the striking features of gender differences in vocabulary is lexical asymmetry, which is expressed in the fact that for men and women there may be different words denoting the same things, but with different stylistic coloring or social meaning. Gender asymmetry also manifests itself in the use of pejorative and exaggeratedly positive terms to describe the behavior of representatives of different sexes. An example is the word "coward", which applies only to women, while there is no similar male equivalent (although the word "coward" denotes male cowardice).

The vocabulary of language is directly related to the perception and interpretation of reality, including the perception of the roles of men and women. Gender stereotypes embedded in language affect how we perceive people and their behavior. For example, in the public consciousness, women are traditionally associated with gentleness, care, and sensuality, while men are associated with determination, strength, and activity. These stereotypes are reflected in the language through the choice of words.

Vocabulary expressing the traditional perception of women's roles: Women are often described using words such as "gentle", "caring", "weak", "sweet", which reinforces the perception of them as dependent, emotional, and subordinate beings. These words can have an impact on how society perceives a woman as a

member of society, whose actions and decisions are most often determined by emotional and caring aspects.

Vocabulary expressing the perception of men's roles: Unlike women, men are more often associated with qualities such as "strength", "leadership", "aggression", "confidence". These words reinforce the stereotypes that men should be determined, capable of action and overcoming difficulties. It also influences the perception of a man's social role as an active participant in external life, in contrast to a woman, whose role is often associated with household duties.

In the professional field, there are also gender differences in vocabulary, which can reflect and reinforce social expectations related to gender. In a number of professions, there is a pronounced gender asymmetry in terminology. For example, terms such as "director", "general manager", and "supervisor" are often used for men in leadership positions, while women in similar positions are often designated with added gender clarification, such as "female director" or "director", which emphasizes exclusivity and the rarity of such a situation. This may help reinforce the stereotype that men should occupy leadership positions "by default".

Vocabulary plays a key role in distinguishing between male and female language practices. Research shows that men and women often use different lexical tools to describe the same phenomena. For example, Goldberg G.L. in the study "Language and Gender" notes that women are more likely to use words expressing emotion and empathy, while men are more likely to use words related to actions and achievements. This observation is related to the cultural norm according to which women are expected to be emotional, while men are expected to be rational and in control [3].

In addition, there is the phenomenon of "women's vocabulary", which includes smaller, more detailed words describing everyday life, feelings, and relationships. An example is the large number of words in Russian to describe different shades of color or states of mind that women use more often.

From the point of view of cognitive linguistics, the use of language is associated with conceptual schemes that form the basis of human thinking. These schemas, or schematic models, are generalized representations of the world that are formed through experience and social interactions. Gender differences in language are often associated with differences in the cognitive schemas that men and women use in the context of communication.

For example, conceptual metaphors such as "life is a journey" or "life is a struggle" may be perceived differently by men and women. Men, who are traditionally more focused on competition and achievement, may more often use metaphors related to struggle, victory, and strength, while women, who are focused on caring and maintaining relationships, may use metaphors related to travel or the process of becoming.

One of the key topics of the study is the analysis of lexical differences in the language of men and women. Vocabulary, as a well-known element of language, often reflects sociocultural expectations and stereotypes related to gender. In the speech of women, one can often observe a higher frequency of using words expressing emotions, feelings and care, while men are

more likely to use words related to actions, achievements, and results.

An example of such a difference can be a comparison of the vocabulary used by women and men to describe interpersonal relationships. Women are more likely to use words such as "caring", "love", "empathy", while men are more likely to use words related to "competition", "success", "strength". This does not always mean that women and men cannot use these words, but research shows that their frequency and context of use may vary depending on the social and cultural context.

In cognitive linguistics, special attention is paid to the analysis of conceptual metaphors that underlie our thought processes. Gender metaphors are one of the clearest examples of such conceptual differences. For example, in Russian there are metaphors reflecting the idea that a woman is the "weaker sex" and a man is the "stronger sex". This metaphorical representation is deeply ingrained in the language and influences the perception of the social role of each of the sexes.

Conceptual metaphors can also be associated with the perception of emotions and behavior. For example, the female emotion of love is often metaphorically represented as "fire" or "river", while for men, love can be associated with "struggle" or "high purpose". This reflects differences in social roles, where women are often assigned emotional and caring roles, while men are assigned rational and achievement roles.

One of the most striking examples of gender metaphors is the idea of a "weak" and a "strong" gender. The metaphor of "a woman as the weaker sex" is deeply rooted in culture and language, associating women with vulnerability, dependence and subordination. At the same time, "man as the stronger sex" presents men as a symbol of power, independence and strength. These metaphors, on the one hand, reflect traditional ideas about men and women, on the other hand, they strengthen and support these stereotypes [3].

Women are characterized by metaphors related to fragility and vulnerability. For example, metaphors such as "crystal vessel", "delicate flower", or "angel's wing" emphasize the physical and emotional fragility of women. This affects the perception of women as weak and in need of protection, which, in turn, shapes a woman's social role as a caring but dependent person.

Men are more often associated with metaphors related to power, control, and achievement. For example, the metaphor "man as a leader" or "man as a defender" emphasizes the dominance of men in public and social life. The metaphor "love as war", which is also often used in relation to men, traces the idea of struggle, conflict and victory. Men are perceived as those who fight and overcome difficulties, which corresponds to traditional male roles in society.

Gender metaphors are found in different languages. For example, such metaphors as "man of steel", "the boss", and "the protector" are common in English. These metaphors actively form the idea of men as strong and domineering personalities. In contrast, metaphors such as "fragile beauty" or "emotional creature" are often applied to women, emphasizing their vulnerability and emotionality.

An interesting example is the Chinese metaphor “a woman is like water”, which emphasizes the softness, flexibility, and malleability of women. While “a man is like a stone” symbolizes strength, rigidity and constancy. This metaphor embodies broader cultural concepts of male and female roles in Chinese society, where men are traditionally perceived as support and protectors, and women as supportive and caring individuals.

Metaphors play an important role in shaping the public perception of men and women. They not only reflect existing gender stereotypes, but also actively reproduce them. Metaphors create images that influence behavior and expectations from people based on their gender. For example, the metaphor of “war” to describe a love relationship can create an image of aggression and conflict, which helps reinforce the stereotype that men should be aggressive and competitive. The metaphor of “weakness” in relation to women supports the stereotype that women should be dependent and caring, as well as vulnerable.

These metaphors also influence an individual’s sense of self and behavior in society. Women who often encounter the metaphor of “tenderness” may perceive themselves as needing protection and care, which affects their behavior and perception of their abilities. Men, in turn, are confronted with the metaphors of “strength” and “leadership”, which creates an expectation for them to achieve success through overcoming difficulties and demonstrating their strength.

An example of lexical differences that can also be explored through the lens of cognitive linguistics is the use of spatial vocabulary. Men and women perceive space differently and often use different metaphors to describe objects and actions related to spatial landmarks. Women tend to use metaphors focused on connection and satisfaction of needs, whereas men may more often turn to metaphors related to the acquisition or control of space [1].

Research shows that men and women often use space and spatial vocabulary in different ways, which may be related to their social roles and cultural expectations. Spatial metaphors and expressions not only reflect reality, but also help to form and strengthen certain social norms and gender stereotypes. For example, metaphors that associate men with spatial activity (for example, “occupy space”, “conquer the world”) emphasize their role as leaders and agents of power, while metaphors that associate women with limitations in space (for example, “limited freedom”, “locked in a house”). They reinforce stereotypes about women’s subordination and dependence.

Spatial vocabulary often serves as a reflection of social norms and stereotypes. Gender differences in the use of spatial vocabulary can be viewed through the lens of cognitive schemas, which are mental structures that help people perceive and interpret the world around them. For example, for women, it is traditionally assumed that their role in society is related to home and family, which can be expressed in the use of metaphors that emphasize the limitations of their “space”. In turn, men are often associated with wider and more open spaces, reflecting their traditional role as leaders and agents of external change.

Men and control over space: Spatial metaphors such as “conquer territory”, “be on top”, “occupy space” are actively used to denote male control over the social or physical environment. These metaphors not only reflect male activity, but also symbolize power and dominance [2].

Women and limited space: Women, in turn, are often associated with spatial metaphors associated with restriction and lack of freedom. For example, the metaphors “shackled space”, “locked in a cage”, “secondary place” are used to describe the limitations in choice for women. These metaphors reinforce stereotypes that a woman’s place is in the home, not in public or political life.

Gender-related stereotypes also have an impact on lexical behavior. Women are often perceived as more emotional and less aggressive in their speech, which is associated with cultural stereotypes about “feminine” gentleness and caring. This, in turn, affects the choice of vocabulary and intonation. Men, on the contrary, are more likely to use aggressive or competitive words, reflecting traditional expectations of “male” determination and strength.

Intonation and other paralinguistic tools also play an important role in gender differences. Women tend to use a more diverse intonation, which is related to their social role in society, where they are often expected to show emotion and expressiveness. Men, in turn, may tend to have a more even, monotonous intonation, which is associated with restraint and control.

Stereotypes about the “feminine” and “masculine” language often lead to negative perceptions of the speech of both sexes. Women who use a “masculine” communication style may be perceived as aggressive or unfeminine, while men who are prone to a “feminine” style risk being perceived as weak or dependent. These stereotypes have a great impact on public perceptions and gender roles in communication.

Linguistic studies of gender differences in speech practices show that language is not only a means of communication, but also an important tool for shaping and maintaining gender roles in society. Differences in the speech of men and women are related to cultural and social norms, which, in turn, affect the perception and distribution of power and status in the social structure [4].

Cognitive linguistics offers a unique approach to the study of gender differences in language, as it allows not only to analyze language as a system of signs, but also to consider it in the context of cognitive processes, social norms and cultural expectations. Gender differences in vocabulary are not accidental; they are deeply rooted in cognitive schemas, social roles, and metaphorical models that men and women use to perceive the world.

References

1. AbdAlgane M. Gendered Language: A Study of Sociolinguistic Theories and Approaches. Asian ESP Journal | Volume 17 Issue 3.1. P. 204-215.
2. Coates J. Women, men and language: a sociolinguistic account of gender differences in language / Jennifer Coates. - 3rd ed. Routledge. Taylor & Francis Group. London-New York, 2004.

3. Goldberg G.L., Roswell B. Reading, Writing, and Gender. Taylor & Francis Ltd, 2002, 190 p.

4. Lakoff R. *Language and Woman's Place*. New York: 1975, Harper & Row.

5. Tannen D. You just don't understand: Women and men in conversation. New York: William Morrow and Co., 1990. 330 p.

6. Бахтин М. *Проблемы речевой коммуникации*. Москва: 1986: Прогресс.